

The following contains the gathered execution environment information from one of our testbed nodes:

```
SUDO_GID=1000
MAIL=/var/mail/USER
USER=USER
HOME=/home/lrl
SUDO_UID=1000
LOGNAME=USER
TERM=xterm-256color
USERNAME=USER
PATH=/usr/local/sbin:/usr/local/bin:/usr/sbin:/usr/bin:/sbin:/bin:/snap/bin
LANG=en_US.UTF-8
LS_COLORS=rs=0:di=01;34:ln=01;36:mh=00:pi=40;33:so=01;35:do=01;35:bd=40;33;01:cd=40;
33;01:or=40;31;01:mi=00:su=37;41:sg=30;43:ca=30;41:tw=30;42:ow=34;42:st=37;44:ex=01;32:
*.tar=01;31:*.tgz=01;31:*.arc=01;31:*.arj=01;31:*.taz=01;31:*.lha=01;31:*.lz4=01;31:*.lzh=01;31:
*.lzma=01;31:*.tlz=01;31:*.txz=01;31:*.tzo=01;31:*.t7z=01;31:*.zip=01;31:*.z=01;31:*.Z=01;31:*.
dz=01;31:*.gz=01;31:*.lrz=01;31:*.lz=01;31:*.lzo=01;31:*.xz=01;31:*.bz2=01;31:*.bz=01;31:*.tbz
=01;31:*.tbz2=01;31:*.tz=01;31:*.deb=01;31:*.rpm=01;31:*.jar=01;31:*.war=01;31:*.ear=01;31:*.
sar=01;31:*.rar=01;31:*.alz=01;31:*.ace=01;31:*.zoo=01;31:*.cpio=01;31:*.7z=01;31:*.rz=01;31:
*.cab=01;31:*.jpg=01;35:*.jpeg=01;35:*.gif=01;35:*.bmp=01;35:*.pbm=01;35:*.pgm=01;35:*.ppm
=01;35:*.tga=01;35:*.xbm=01;35:*.xpm=01;35:*.tif=01;35:*.tiff=01;35:*.png=01;35:*.svg=01;35:*.
svgz=01;35:*.mng=01;35:*.pcx=01;35:*.mov=01;35:*.mpg=01;35:*.mpeg=01;35:*.m2v=01;35:*.
mkv=01;35:*.webm=01;35:*.ogm=01;35:*.mp4=01;35:*.m4v=01;35:*.mp4v=01;35:*.vob=01;35:*.
qt=01;35:*.nuv=01;35:*.wmv=01;35:*.asf=01;35:*.rm=01;35:*.rmvb=01;35:*.flc=01;35:*.avi=01;3
5:*.fli=01;35:*.flv=01;35:*.gl=01;35:*.dl=01;35:*.xcf=01;35:*.xwd=01;35:*.yuv=01;35:*.cgm=01;3
5:*.emf=01;35:*.ogv=01;35:*.ogx=01;35:*.aac=00;36:*.au=00;36:*.flac=00;36:*.m4a=00;36:*.mid
=00;36:*.midi=00;36:*.mka=00;36:*.mp3=00;36:*.mpc=00;36:*.ogg=00;36:*.ra=00;36:*.wav=00;
36:*.oga=00;36:*.opus=00;36:*.spx=00;36:*.xspf=00;36:
SUDO_COMMAND=./collect_environment.sh
SHELL=/bin/bash
SUDO_USER=lrl
PWD=/home/USER
+ lsb_release -a
No LSB modules are available.
Distributor ID: Ubuntu
Description:   Ubuntu 16.04.6 LTS
Release:      16.04
Codename:     xenial
+ uname -a
Linux host15 4.15.0-96-generic #97~16.04.1-Ubuntu SMP Wed Apr 1 03:03:31 UTC 2020
x86_64 x86_64 x86_64 GNU/Linux
+ lscpu
```

Architecture: x86_64
CPU op-mode(s): 32-bit, 64-bit
Byte Order: Little Endian
CPU(s): 12
On-line CPU(s) list: 0-11
Thread(s) per core: 2
Core(s) per socket: 6
Socket(s): 1
NUMA node(s): 1
Vendor ID: GenuineIntel
CPU family: 6
Model: 63
Model name: Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2620 v3 @ 2.40GHz
Stepping: 2
CPU MHz: 1198.874
CPU max MHz: 3200.0000
CPU min MHz: 1200.0000
BogoMIPS: 4794.59
Virtualization: VT-x
L1d cache: 32K
L1i cache: 32K
L2 cache: 256K
L3 cache: 15360K
NUMA node0 CPU(s): 0-11
Flags: fpu vme de pse tsc msr pae mce cx8 apic sep mtrr pge mca cmov pat pse36
clflush dts acpi mmx fxsr sse sse2 ss ht tm pbe syscall nx pdpe1gb rdtscp lm constant_tsc
arch_perfmon pebs bts rep_good nopl xtopology nonstop_tsc cpuid aperfmperf pni pclmulqdq
dtes64 monitor ds_cpl vmx smx est tm2 ssse3 sdbg fma cx16 xtpr pdcm pcid dca sse4_1
sse4_2 x2apic movbe popcnt tsc_deadline_timer aes xsave avx f16c rdrand lahf_lm abm
cpuid_fault epb invpcid_single pti ssbd ibrs ibpb stibp tpr_shadow vnmi flexpriority ept vpid
fsgsbase tsc_adjust bmi1 avx2 smep bmi2 erms invpcid cqm xsaveopt cqm_llc cqm_occup_llc
dtherm ida arat pln pts md_clear flush_l1d
+ cat /proc/meminfo
MemTotal: 24583384 kB
MemFree: 17715948 kB
MemAvailable: 23471924 kB
Buffers: 458568 kB
Cached: 5572240 kB
SwapCached: 0 kB
Active: 1973808 kB
Inactive: 4199312 kB
Active(anon): 242328 kB
Inactive(anon): 171988 kB

Active(file): 1731480 kB
Inactive(file): 4027324 kB
Unevictable: 0 kB
Mlocked: 0 kB
SwapTotal: 999420 kB
SwapFree: 999420 kB
Dirty: 188 kB
Writeback: 0 kB
AnonPages: 142248 kB
Mapped: 116060 kB
Shmem: 272008 kB
Slab: 460060 kB
SReclaimable: 401264 kB
SUnreclaim: 58796 kB
KernelStack: 5324 kB
PageTables: 11300 kB
NFS_Unstable: 0 kB
Bounce: 0 kB
WritebackTmp: 0 kB
CommitLimit: 13291112 kB
Committed_AS: 1517992 kB
VmallocTotal: 34359738367 kB
VmallocUsed: 0 kB
VmallocChunk: 0 kB
HardwareCorrupted: 0 kB
AnonHugePages: 0 kB
ShmemHugePages: 0 kB
ShmemPmdMapped: 0 kB
CmaTotal: 0 kB
CmaFree: 0 kB
HugePages_Total: 0
HugePages_Free: 0
HugePages_Rsvd: 0
HugePages_Surp: 0
Hugepagesize: 2048 kB
DirectMap4k: 188196 kB
DirectMap2M: 8101888 kB
DirectMap1G: 18874368 kB
+ inxi -F -c0
./collect_environment.sh: 14: ./collect_environment.sh: inxi: not found
+ lsblk -a
NAME MAJ:MIN RM SIZE RO TYPE MOUNTPOINT
loop1 7:1 0 0 loop

```

loop6 7:6 0 0 loop
loop4 7:4 0 0 loop
loop2 7:2 0 0 loop
loop0 7:0 0 0 loop
loop7 7:7 0 0 loop
sda 8:0 0 931.5G 0 disk
├─sda2 8:2 0 1K 0 part
├─sda5 8:5 0 976M 0 part [SWAP]
└─sda1 8:1 0 930.6G 0 part /
loop5 7:5 0 0 loop
loop3 7:3 0 0 loop

```

+ lsscsi -s

./collect_environment.sh: 16: ./collect_environment.sh: lsscsi: not found

+ module list

./collect_environment.sh: 17: ./collect_environment.sh: module: not found

+ nvidia-smi

./collect_environment.sh: 18: ./collect_environment.sh: nvidia-smi: not found

+ lshw -short -quiet -sanitize

+ cat

H/W path	Device	Class	Description
=====			
	system		PowerEdge R430 (SKU=NotProvided;ModelName=PowerEdge R430)
/0	bus	03XKDV	
/0/0	memory	64KiB	BIOS
/0/400	processor		Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2620 v3 @ 2.40GHz
/0/400/700	memory		384KiB L1 cache
/0/400/701	memory		1536KiB L2 cache
/0/400/702	memory		15MiB L3 cache
/0/401	processor		CPU [empty]
/0/1000	memory		24GiB System Memory
/0/1000/0	memory		8GiB DIMM Synchronous 2133 MHz (0.5 ns)
/0/1000/1	memory		8GiB DIMM Synchronous 2133 MHz (0.5 ns)
/0/1000/2	memory		8GiB DIMM Synchronous 2133 MHz (0.5 ns)
/0/1000/3	memory		[empty]
/0/1000/4	memory		[empty]
/0/1000/5	memory		[empty]
/0/1000/6	memory		[empty]
/0/1000/7	memory		[empty]
/0/1000/8	memory		[empty]
/0/1000/9	memory		[empty]
/0/1000/a	memory		[empty]
/0/1000/b	memory		[empty]

/0/100	bridge		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DMI2
/0/100/1	bridge		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 PCI Express Root Port 1
/0/100/3	bridge		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 PCI Express Root Port 3
/0/100/3.2	bridge		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 PCI Express Root Port 3
/0/100/3.2/0	enp5s0f0	network	NetXtreme II BCM57810 10 Gigabit Ethernet
/0/100/3.2/0.1	enp5s0f1	network	NetXtreme II BCM57810 10 Gigabit Ethernet
/0/100/5	generic		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Address Map, VTd_Misc, System Management
/0/100/5.1	generic		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Hot Plug
/0/100/5.2	generic		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 RAS, Control Status and Global Errors
/0/100/5.4	generic		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 I/O APIC
/0/100/11	generic		C610/X99 series chipset SPSR
/0/100/11.4	storage		C610/X99 series chipset sSATA Controller [AHCI mode]
/0/100/16	communication		C610/X99 series chipset MEI Controller #1
/0/100/16.1	communication		C610/X99 series chipset MEI Controller #2
/0/100/1a	bus		C610/X99 series chipset USB Enhanced Host Controller #2
/0/100/1a/1	usb1	bus	EHCI Host Controller
/0/100/1a/1/1		bus	USB hub
/0/100/1a/1/1/4		input	Keyboard
/0/100/1a/1/1/6		bus	Gadget USB HUB
/0/100/1c	bridge		C610/X99 series chipset PCI Express Root Port #1
/0/100/1c.1	bridge		C610/X99 series chipset PCI Express Root Port #2
/0/100/1c.1/0	bridge		SH7758 PCIe Switch [PS]
/0/100/1c.1/0/0	bridge		SH7758 PCIe Switch [PS]
/0/100/1c.1/0/0/0	bridge		SH7758 PCIe-PCI Bridge [PPB]
/0/100/1c.1/0/0/0/0	display		G200eR2
/0/100/1c.2	bridge		C610/X99 series chipset PCI Express Root Port #3
/0/100/1c.2/0	eno1	network	NetXtreme BCM5720 Gigabit Ethernet PCIe
/0/100/1c.2/0.1	eno2	network	NetXtreme BCM5720 Gigabit Ethernet PCIe
/0/100/1c.3	bridge		C610/X99 series chipset PCI Express Root Port #4
/0/100/1c.3/0	eno3	network	NetXtreme BCM5720 Gigabit Ethernet PCIe
/0/100/1c.3/0.1	eno4	network	NetXtreme BCM5720 Gigabit Ethernet PCIe
/0/100/1d	bus		C610/X99 series chipset USB Enhanced Host Controller #1
/0/100/1d/1	usb2	bus	EHCI Host Controller
/0/100/1d/1/1		bus	USB hub
/0/100/1f	bridge		C610/X99 series chipset LPC Controller
/0/100/1f.2	storage		C610/X99 series chipset 6-Port SATA Controller [AHCI mode]
/0/b	generic		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 R3 QPI Link 0 & 1 Monitoring
/0/b.1	generic		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 R3 QPI Link 0 & 1 Monitoring
/0/b.2	generic		Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 R3 QPI Link 0 & 1

Monitoring

/0/c	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Unicast Registers
/0/c.1	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Unicast Registers
/0/c.2	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Unicast Registers
/0/c.3	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Unicast Registers
/0/c.4	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Unicast Registers
/0/c.5	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Unicast Registers
/0/f	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Buffered Ring Agent
/0/f.1	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Buffered Ring Agent
/0/f.4	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 System Address Decoder & Broadcast Registers
/0/f.5	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 System Address Decoder & Broadcast Registers
/0/f.6	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 System Address Decoder & Broadcast Registers
/0/10	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 PCIe Ring Interface
/0/10.1	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 PCIe Ring Interface
/0/10.5	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Scratchpad & Semaphore Registers
/0/10.6	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Scratchpad & Semaphore Registers
/0/10.7	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Scratchpad & Semaphore Registers
/0/12	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Home Agent 0
/0/12.1	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Home Agent 0
/0/12.2	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Home Agent 0 Debug
/0/13	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Target Address, Thermal & RAS Registers
/0/13.1	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Target Address, Thermal & RAS Registers
/0/13.2	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel Target Address Decoder
/0/13.3	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel Target Address Decoder
/0/13.4	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel Target Address Decoder
/0/13.5	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel Target Address Decoder
/0/13.6	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO Channel 0/1 Broadcast
/0/13.7	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO Global Broadcast
/0/14	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel 0 Thermal Control

/0/14.1	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel 1 Thermal Control
/0/14.2	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel 0 ERROR Registers
/0/14.3	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel 1 ERROR Registers
/0/14.4	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO (VMSE) 0 & 1
/0/14.5	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO (VMSE) 0 & 1
/0/14.6	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO (VMSE) 0 & 1
/0/14.7	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO (VMSE) 0 & 1
/0/15	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel 2 Thermal Control
/0/15.1	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel 3 Thermal Control
/0/15.2	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel 2 ERROR Registers
/0/15.3	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 0 Channel 3 ERROR Registers
/0/16	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 1 Target Address, Thermal & RAS Registers
/0/16.6	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO Channel 2/3 Broadcast
/0/16.7	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO Global Broadcast
/0/17	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Integrated Memory Controller 1 Channel 0 Thermal Control
/0/17.4	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO (VMSE) 2 & 3
/0/17.5	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO (VMSE) 2 & 3
/0/17.6	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO (VMSE) 2 & 3
/0/17.7	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 DDRIO (VMSE) 2 & 3
/0/1e	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Power Control Unit
/0/1e.1	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Power Control Unit
/0/1e.2	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Power Control Unit
/0/1e.3	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Power Control Unit
/0/1e.4	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 Power Control Unit
/0/1f	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 VCU
/0/1f.2	generic	Xeon E7 v3/Xeon E5 v3/Core i7 VCU
/0/1	scsi0	storage
/0/1/0.0.0	/dev/sda	disk 1TB ST1000NM0033-9ZM
/0/1/0.0.0/1	/dev/sda1	volume 930GiB EXT4 volume
/0/1/0.0.0/2	/dev/sda2	volume 976MiB Extended partition
/0/1/0.0.0/2/5	/dev/sda5	volume 976MiB Linux swap / Solaris partition